

Project-Based Learning Methodology for Teaching Software Engineering: Experience in the Information Technology Program at Universidad Técnica Luis Vargas Torres de Esmeraldas (UTLVTE)

Stalin Francis

¹Universidad Técnica Luis Vargas Torres, Ecuador;stalin.francis@utlvt.edu.ec

Abstract

The teaching of Software Engineering in higher education faces significant challenges related to student engagement, practical skill development, and the integration of theory with real-world problem solving. This study presents an educational experience based on the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology applied in the Software Engineering course of the Information Technology program at Universidad Técnica Luis Vargas Torres de Esmeraldas, Ecuador. The objective of this research was to analyze the impact of PBL on student learning, participation, and understanding of software development processes. The methodology involved the design and implementation of collaborative projects aligned with real software development scenarios, supported by continuous assessment strategies. Data were collected through academic performance records, project evaluations, and student perception surveys. The results indicate that over 96 % of students reported high satisfaction and perceived improved professional readiness in motivation, teamwork, and the application of theoretical concepts to practical contexts. The study concludes that PBL is an effective pedagogical strategy for teaching Software Engineering and supports the integration of active learning methodologies in technology-related higher education programs.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning; Software Engineering Education; Active Learning; Higher Education

1. Introduction

Teaching Software Engineering remains a significant challenge in technological degree programs, particularly in contexts where a weak connection between academic theory and professional practice persists. According to the IEEE (2022), more than 60 % of computer science programs in Latin America exhibit shortcomings in the practical preparation of graduates, negatively affecting their performance in dynamic, project-oriented work environments. These limitations are more pronounced in public universities facing budget constraints, limited infrastructure, and restricted access to up-to-date technologies.

At the Universidad Técnica Luis Vargas Torres de Esmeraldas (UTLVTE), located in a region with low technological development, the course Software Engineering I has traditionally relied on lecture-based instruction, resulting in limited achievement of applied learning outcomes. This gap between academic training and labor market requirements motivated the adoption of a pedagogical approach based on Project-Based Learning (PBL),

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aimed at fostering active, collaborative learning through engagement with real-world problems.

Previous studies have demonstrated that PBL is an effective methodology in technical education, as it integrates technical competencies with transversal skills such as teamwork, communication, and time management (Prince, 2004; Smith, 2019). In this instructional experience, PBL was implemented through a course redesign that incorporated agile methodologies (Scrum) and the use of software development and deployment tools, including GitHub and Model–View–Controller (MVC) frameworks.

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of PBL on the development of technical and attitudinal competencies in students enrolled in Software Engineering I, through the implementation of a real-world project and the analysis of students' perceptions using a structured survey. Accordingly, the following research question is addressed: How does the application of Project-Based Learning influence students' perceptions of usefulness, motivation, and competency development in Software Engineering I?

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Design

This study adopted a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional and descriptive design. Its purpose was to analyze students' perceptions of the effectiveness of Project-Based Learning (PBL) implemented in the Software Engineering I course during the first academic semester of 2024 at the Universidad Técnica Luis Vargas Torres de Esmeraldas (UTLVTE).

2.2. Population and Sample

The sample consisted of 50 fifth-semester students enrolled in the Information Technology program who completed the Software Engineering I course in sections A and B. Of the total participants, 8 were female and 42 male, with ages ranging from 20 to 26 years. A purposive, non-probabilistic sampling method was employed, using convenience sampling due to the students' direct participation in the PBL-based instructional experience.

2.3. Data Collection Technique and Instrument

Data were collected using a structured satisfaction survey specifically designed for this study. The instrument was validated through expert judgment by three faculty members with experience in higher education and instrument design. The survey consisted of:

- Ten closed-ended items using a four-point Likert scale (ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree"), aimed at measuring perceptions of usefulness, dynamism, applicability, and overall satisfaction with the methodology.
- One open-ended item designed to collect qualitative feedback and suggestions for improving the teaching–learning process.

The survey was administered anonymously and voluntarily at the end of the academic term through a digital questionnaire.

2.4. Procedure

Throughout the semester, the course was redesigned following the PBL model. Practical activities were organized around the development of a real-world project consisting of a functional web system, implemented using the Scrum agile methodology, teamwork, technical documentation, tools such as GitHub, and server deployment. At the end of the course, students completed the survey as part of the closing session. Data were processed and analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) with the support of Microsoft Excel to identify general satisfaction trends and areas for improvement.

2.5. Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in strict accordance with ethical principles of educational research. Prior to data collection, participants were informed about the purpose of the study and assured that their participation was voluntary, that they could withdraw at any time, and that all information collected would remain anonymous and confidential. No sensitive data or personal identifiers were collected. The results were used exclusively for academic purposes and for improving teaching practices, in compliance with the principles established by the Organic Law of Higher Education of Ecuador and the institutional guidelines of UTLVTE. Furthermore, it was guaranteed that participation in the study had no influence on students' grades or academic evaluation.

Figure 1. Learning and assessment activities implemented in the Project-Based Learning approach for the Software Engineering I course.

The activities illustrated in Figure 1 are designed to foster learning development across three complementary dimensions.

- **Activity A**, aimed at strengthening active listening and effective communication. This activity seeks to encourage class attendance and participation, which are assessed through attendance records and students' contributions during question-and-answer sessions related to the topics addressed.
- **Activity B**, focused on practical and experiential learning through the resolution of analysis and design workshops, as well as the application of software development and programming tools.
- **Activity C**, intended to promote autonomous learning through the reading of scientific articles, whose comprehension is assessed via participation in academic discussion forums.

These activities are distributed across the different units of the two academic terms. Together with partial summative assessments, they consolidate the students' formative learning process.

The instructional process began with the presentation of the instructor and students, followed by a detailed review of the syllabus, semester planning, and classroom project during the first two sessions. In each instructional unit, one session was devoted to addressing theoretical fundamentals, complemented by an autonomous learning activity (C1-1, C1-2, C1-3, C1-4) based on the reading of an academic article that contributed to broadening the topic under study [Roselló et al. \(2002\)](#), [Canós et al. \(2004\)](#), [Castillo Yagual and Coronel Suárez \(2023\)](#), [Gómez-Zea et al. \(2023\)](#). In subsequent sessions, the Scrum agile methodology was introduced, and students were organized into groups of five with defined roles (Product Owner, Scrum Master, and Team Developers), following pedagogical models that emphasize the relevance of collaborative work [Kuz \(2021\)](#).

During the first practical phase, students developed skills related to analysis and design. Activity B1-1 consisted of a workshop focused on the creation of user stories, in which each student developed ten user stories, demonstrating creativity and understanding of the system to be developed. Within the same workshop, students also created prototypes representing the initial system interfaces. This process culminated in the development of a web page and its upload to GitHub, allowing the instructor to deploy each repository on a virtual machine for evaluation purposes. This activity was reinforced through Activity B1-2, in which each group of five students performed a dramatization recreating the Agile-Scrum process. Together, these activities covered the initial stages of the software life cycle: requirements elicitation, analysis, and design [Boehm \(1988\)](#).

In the second partial assessment period, students addressed the stages of software development, maintenance, and deployment. During Activity B2-1, the Model-View-Controller (MVC) architecture and the use of GitHub were introduced. The Scrum Master of each group created a repository containing the *eys-mvc* framework, which was specifically developed to support the didactic understanding of the MVC pattern. This initial system was deployed on a real server. Finally, in Activity B2-2, students performed maintenance tasks on the application in accordance with the user stories defined in Activity B1-1. These tasks promoted practical learning in real-world environments aligned with current trends in the technology industry [Fitzgerald \(2006\)](#).

In parallel, each practical-experimental activity was supported by presentations in which students had the opportunity to reinforce their learning experience by explaining their development process. These presentations corresponded to Activities A1-1, A1-2, A2-1, and A2-2, fostering analytical skills and the ability to develop creative solutions to complex problems. This comprehensive approach enabled students to experience both the theoretical and practical dimensions of agile software development, achieving significant outcomes in terms of knowledge acquisition and the creation of functional products. All activities used to assess the topics addressed, as summarized in [Table 1](#), were organized and incorporated into the semester plan and appropriately distributed over time to ensure that students could complete each task without interfering with activities from other courses, as detailed in [Table A1](#).

Table 1. Units, topics, and learning activities in the Software Engineering I course.

Unit	Original Topic	Adapted Topic	Learning Activities
Unit I	Software and Software Engineering	Introduction to Software Engineering	C1-1: Discussion forum based on the article "Is there a crisis in educational software?". B1-1: Workshop on user story creation and interface prototype design for a web application. A1-1: Group presentation using slides to explain the developed user stories and interfaces.
Unit II	Software Management	Software Project Management and Agile Scrum Methodology	C1-2: Discussion forum based on the scientific article "Agile Methodologies in Software Development".

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Unit	Original Topic	Adapted Topic	Learning Activities
			<p>B1-2: Role-playing activity in which student groups simulate the Agile-Scrum framework.</p> <p>A1-2: Slide-based presentation describing the Scrum process and the artifacts produced.</p> <p>E1: First partial summative assessment.</p>
Unit III	System and Software Requirements Analysis	System Requirements, Software Architecture, Frameworks, and GitHub	<p>C2-1: Discussion forum assessing reading comprehension of the article "PHP Frameworks Based on the Model-View-Controller Architecture for Web Application Development".</p> <p>B2-1: Development and deployment of the first web application using an MVC-based framework and version control with Git and GitHub.</p> <p>A2-1: Technical presentation describing the MVC-based web application developed.</p>
Unit IV	Software Dimensions	Software Sizing and Evolution	<p>C2-2: Discussion forum based on the scientific article "Optimization of Documentation in Agile Software Projects: Best Practices and Artifacts in the SCRUM Framework".</p> <p>B2-2: Maintenance and evolution of the previously developed web application to improve functionality and appearance.</p> <p>A2-2: Technical presentation explaining the improvements made to the application.</p> <p>E2: Final summative assessment.</p>

To reduce the complexity of rubric application, two assessment criteria were considered for Activities C1-1, C1-2, C2-1, and C2-2: students' presentation performance (50%) and the quality and clarity of their contributions (50%). For Activity B1-1, assessment was based on the quality of the user stories developed (50%) and the quality of the interface designs (50%). In Activity B2-1, the same assessment criteria used for the discussion forums were applied. For Activities B2-1 and B2-2, evaluation considered the code submitted to GitHub as evidence of student work (50%) and the functional deployment of the application (50%). Regarding Activities A1-1, A1-2, A2-1, and A2-2, assessment was based on the quality of the presentation slides (25%), the quality and clarity of the oral presentation (25%), and an additional attendance factor. Students who attended all eight classes within the unit received the remaining 50% of the score.

The following figure illustrates the relationships among the different activities, showing how each activity contributes to the understanding of subsequent ones and how,

collectively, they support the achievement of the learning objectives and the development of a high-quality information system.

Figure 2. Relationship between learning and assessment activities implemented in the Project-Based Learning approach for the Software Engineering I course.

3. Results

3.1. Planning

The Software Engineering I course is offered in the fifth semester of the Information Technology program. It has a duration of four months and a weekly workload of five face-to-face hours, distributed into three hours of theoretical instruction and two hours of experimental practice, in addition to 2.5 hours allocated to autonomous learning.

The academic plan comprises a total of 32 sessions, organized into two weekly sessions over a 16-week period. Table A1 presents the semester plan, detailing each of the 32 sessions by indicating the week number, the position of the session within the week (first or second day), and the location where the session is conducted, either in the physical classroom or in the virtual classroom for tutorial sessions delivered via Google Meet.

The plan also specifies the use of chroma key technology settings for video recordings when required by the session. For each session, the topic addressed, the learning activities, and the pedagogical teaching-learning methodology are indicated, with the aim of providing a precise and comprehensive description of the entire formative process.

3.2. Session Development

The development of each session was conducted as follows:

Unit I

In **Session #1**, entitled "**Instructor, course, and student introduction; diagnostic assessment and delivery of the course plan**", the instructor introduced the course and invited each student to briefly introduce themselves by answering questions related to their educational background, motivations for choosing the program, and professional aspirations. This activity facilitated an initial connection and contributed to the creation of a

welcoming learning environment. Subsequently, a diagnostic assessment was administered using a Google Form to evaluate students' prior knowledge at the beginning of the course. Finally, the syllabus, semester plan, and classroom project were provided to students for review in preparation for the following session.

In **Session #2**, entitled "**Review and analysis of the syllabus, semester plan, classroom project, and diagnostic assessment**", a detailed analysis of the course planning was conducted. The topics to be addressed, the proposed learning activities, and the Project-Based Learning methodology guiding the course were presented. Particular emphasis was placed on the classroom project and its scheduled activities, highlighting the importance of adhering to established timelines to ensure the achievement of learning objectives. At the end of the session, students were instructed to review assigned materials (videos and slides) in preparation for the next class.

In **Session #3**, entitled "**Introduction to Software Engineering with emphasis on the software life cycle and Agile Scrum methodology**", theoretical foundations of Software Engineering were introduced, with particular attention to the software life cycle, development methodologies, and their evolution. The Scrum agile methodology was examined in depth, emphasizing project management principles and team roles. During this session, student groups of five members were formed, and Scrum roles were assigned. At the end of the session, the autonomous learning activity C1-1 was assigned to reinforce the concepts addressed.

In **Session #4**, entitled "**Discussion of the scientific article from Activity C1-1, presentation of an information system, and user registration process**", the scientific article "Is There a Crisis in Educational Software?" was discussed. This activity aimed to raise awareness of the importance of developing and maintaining educational information systems. Students were provided with a laboratory practice guide (GPL-IS1-001), which detailed the procedures for accessing the web platform, registering as users, and exploring available modules such as Events and Portfolio. The objective was to enable students to identify limitations and improvement opportunities in educational software by linking theoretical analysis with practical exploration.

In **Session #5**, entitled "**Discussion forum: execution of Activity C1-1**", each Scrum group participated in a discussion forum lasting 10 to 15 minutes, in which the assigned article was analyzed. Detailed feedback was provided, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement in student presentations, with the aim of enhancing future academic performance.

In **Session #6**, conducted in the computer laboratory under the topic "**Project exploration and analysis: Academic management information system and introduction to user stories**", students explored the modules of the academic information system used in the course, guided by a laboratory manual. Due to security constraints, access to certain modules was restricted. The instructor provided explanations, and students recorded observations. A brief introduction to user stories and their formulation was also provided, supported by instructional slides.

In **Session #7**, entitled "**Execution of Activity B1-1: User story and interface prototype workshop for an academic management information system**", a review of user story concepts was conducted using instructional slides. This session also served to assess

pending instances of Activity A1-1. Subsequently, students were provided with a detailed workshop guide explaining the procedural steps for developing user stories and prototypes, which constituted Activity B1-1.

In **Session #8**, entitled “**Execution of Activity A1-1: Presentation of work developed in Activity B1-1**”, students created and delivered slide-based presentations explaining the procedures and outcomes of Activity B1-1. Presentations were delivered by Scrum teams, recorded for assessment purposes, and made available to students to support self-evaluation and improvement.

Unit II

In **Session #9**, entitled “**Software project management through video analysis and guided discussion**”, students reflected on fundamental questions related to project management and software project failures. A video on software project management was presented, followed by an instructor-led analysis of its key concepts.

In **Session #10**, conducted in the computer laboratory under the topic “**Project management and use of the Jira tool**”, students were introduced to Jira as a project management platform, including the creation and assignment of user stories and responsibilities.

In **Session #11**, entitled “**Discussion of the scientific article for Activity C1-2**”, the instructor guided a review of the article “Agile Methodologies in Software Development”, preparing students for their participation in the discussion forum.

In **Session #12**, entitled “**Execution of Activity C1-2: Discussion forum on Agile Methodologies in Software Development**”, each Scrum group participated in a recorded forum session lasting 10 to 15 minutes. Green screen technology and chroma key techniques were applied to edit and share the videos, enabling self-assessment among students.

In **Session #13**, entitled “**Review of Activity B1-2: Scrum methodology dramatization**”, the Agile Scrum framework was reviewed, the dramatization script was presented, and videos from previous cohorts were analyzed to identify strengths and weaknesses.

In **Session #14**, entitled “**Scrum methodology dramatization**”, students performed dramatizations of Scrum meetings using a green screen setup, with each enactment lasting between 10 and 15 minutes.

In **Session #15**, entitled “**Assignment of user stories using Jira**”, students organized responsibilities within Jira and selected appropriate settings for continuing the Scrum dramatization activities.

In **Session #16**, entitled “**First partial assessment**”, students completed the summative evaluation corresponding to the first assessment period.

Unit III

In **Session #17**, entitled “**Requirements documentation**”, a model document of functional and non-functional requirements was presented. Students replicated and adapted the document for their assigned system module.

In **Session #18**, entitled “**Review of requirements documentation**”, submitted documents were evaluated, and feedback was provided to address identified strengths and weaknesses.

In **Session #19**, entitled “**Model–View–Controller software architecture and frameworks**”, an introduction to the MVC architecture and commonly used frameworks was delivered.

In **Session #20**, entitled “**Discussion of the scientific article for Activity C2-1**”, an academic article on MVC architecture and PHP frameworks was reviewed as preparation for the autonomous learning activity C2-1.

In **Session #21**, conducted in the computer laboratory under the topic “**Use of GitHub and repositories**”, students created GitHub accounts, configured repositories, and uploaded assigned modules following a laboratory guide.

In **Session #22**, entitled “**Practical use of Git and GitHub repositories**”, students reinforced repository management skills by configuring and uploading project modules.

In **Session #23**, entitled “**Deployment of the SICA module**”, students deployed their assigned modules using the laboratory guide.

In **Session #24**, Activity A2-1 was conducted, consisting of an oral presentation supported by slides explaining software architecture and the functionality developed in Activity B2-1. Deployment activities continued during the session.

Unit IV

In **Session #25**, entitled “**Introduction to software sizing and agile estimation techniques**”, concepts such as story points and Planning Poker were introduced, followed by a practical workshop applying estimation techniques to previously developed user stories.

In **Session #26**, entitled “**Planning tools: Use of ClickUp**”, students received training on the ClickUp platform for task planning and monitoring activities A, B, and C derived from user stories.

In **Session #27**, entitled “**Discussion of the scientific article on agile documentation optimization**”, Activity C2-2 was introduced through a structured review of the assigned article.

In **Session #28**, entitled “**Execution of Activity C2-2: Scientific article discussion forum**”, each Scrum group participated in a recorded discussion forum using chroma key techniques, and videos were shared through the course communication channels.

In **Session #29**, entitled “**Review of Activity B2-2: Application maintenance**”, maintenance of a system module was demonstrated, and assessment rubrics were explained.

In **Session #30**, feedback was provided on Activity B2-2, focusing on backend and frontend improvements. Guidelines and rubrics for Activity A2-2 were also presented.

In **Session #31**, Activity A2-2 was conducted through oral presentations supported by slides, in which each Scrum group explained technical improvements to the system. Presentations were recorded and edited using chroma key techniques.

Finally, in **Session #32**, entitled “**Final summative assessment**”, a comprehensive evaluation was administered to assess students’ knowledge, skills, and competencies acquired throughout the course.

3.3. Satisfaction Survey

In response to the statement “*How useful did you find the activities carried out for understanding the key concepts of the software life cycle?*”, the response categories “Very useful” and “Useful” accounted for the majority of responses (68% and 30%, respectively), whereas the option “Slightly useful” was selected by only 2% of participants.

Regarding the statement “*How would you rate the teamwork dynamics using Scrum roles?*”, the categories “Very effective” and “Effective” received 56% and 40% of responses, respectively, while “Slightly effective” and “Ineffective” each accounted for 2%.

For the statement “*How clear was your learning of the Scrum agile methodology after the dramatization activity?*”, responses were mainly concentrated in “Very clear” (50%) and “Clear” (44%), with “Slightly clear” representing the remaining 6%.

In response to the statement “*How practical was it to interact directly with users for requirements elicitation?*”, the categories “Very practical” and “Practical” accounted for 54% and 36% of responses, respectively, whereas “Slightly practical” and “Not practical” were selected by 6% and 4% of respondents.

Regarding the statement “*How valuable was the experience of developing web interface prototypes?*”, most responses fell under “Very valuable” (50%) and “Valuable” (46%), while “Slightly valuable” accounted for 4%.

For the statement “*How do you evaluate the presentation of projects at the science fair and open house?*”, the categories “Very satisfactory” and “Satisfactory” represented 44% and 50% of responses, respectively, whereas “Slightly satisfactory” accounted for 6%.

In response to the statement “*How accessible was the use of GitHub for uploading the MVC module?*”, responses were concentrated in “Very accessible” (45%) and “Accessible” (44%), while “Slightly accessible” was selected by 10% of participants.

Regarding the statement “*How attractive did you find the use of the Chroma Key technique for the virtual presentation of the MVC architecture?*”, the categories “Very attractive” and “Attractive” accounted for 32% and 54% of responses, respectively. In contrast, “Slightly attractive” and “Not attractive” represented 12% and 2%.

For the statement “*Do you prefer learning through practical activities and projects such as those implemented, compared to receiving only traditional content and assessments?*”, responses were evenly distributed between “I definitely prefer practical activities” (50%) and “I prefer practical activities combined with some traditional theory” (50%).

In response to the statement “*Do you feel that Project-Based Learning is more effective for your training than traditional assessments?*”, the categories “Strongly agree” and “Agree” accounted for 44% each, while “Disagree” represented 12%.

Regarding the statement “Do you consider that the activities implemented better prepare you for professional challenges than traditional methods?”, responses were concentrated in “Strongly agree” (48%) and “Agree” (52%).

For the statement “Overall, how satisfied are you with the activities implemented in this course?”, the majority of respondents selected “Very satisfied” (32%) and “Satisfied” (66%), while “Slightly satisfied” was selected by 2%.

Finally, in response to the statement “Would you recommend this methodology to other students in the program?”, 60% of participants selected “Definitely yes” and 40% selected “Probably yes”.

3.4. Response to the Open-Ended Question

To provide students with the opportunity to freely express their opinions and contribute suggestions for improvement, an open-ended question was included in the survey. The responses obtained are summarized in Appendix B (Table A2). The results of the survey administered to the 50 students enrolled in the Software Engineering I course allowed for the evaluation of the perceived effectiveness of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology implemented during the 2024-1S semester. The main findings are presented below, organized into thematic categories.

3.4.1. Content Understanding and Theory–Practice Integration

A total of 98% of students rated the activities carried out as “Very useful” (68%) or “Useful” (30%) for understanding the key concepts of the software life cycle. This result suggests that the integration of theoretical and practical components facilitated meaningful learning, supporting the effectiveness of the adopted pedagogical approach.

3.4.2. Collaborative Work and Agile Methodologies

Regarding teamwork dynamics under defined roles based on the Scrum methodology, 96% of students considered the experience “Very effective” (56%) or “Effective” (40%). In addition, 94% reported that the dramatization of the Scrum methodology contributed to a “Very clear” (50%) or “Clear” (44%) understanding of the agile approach.

3.4.3. Practical Application of Tools and Processes

Ninety percent of students reported that interacting directly with users for requirements elicitation was “Very practical” (54%) or “Practical” (36%), reflecting the strengthening of technical skills in real-world contexts. Furthermore, 96% of respondents evaluated the experience of developing web interface prototypes as “Very valuable” or “Valuable”. Regarding the use of GitLab (or GitHub, depending on the final version of the course), 89% of students considered the tool “Very accessible” or “Accessible”, indicating an appropriate integration of industry-standard technologies.

3.4.4. Motivation, Satisfaction, and Methodological Preference

All respondents (100%) expressed a preference for the practical PBL approach over traditional teaching methods, either exclusively (50%) or in combination with traditional theoretical instruction (50%). Likewise, 96% of students indicated that they were “Very satisfied” or “Satisfied” with the activities implemented in the course, and all participants stated that they would recommend this methodology to other students in the program.

3.4.5. Qualitative Feedback

In the open-ended responses, students highlighted strengths such as the strong connection between theory and practice, collaborative work, and the motivation generated by dynamic activities such as Scrum dramatizations and project presentations. Areas for

improvement included the need for clearer role definitions within teams, more continuous feedback throughout the projects, and a fairer assessment of individual contributions.

4. Discussion

The results obtained indicate that the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PBL) in the Software Engineering I course had a highly positive impact on students' perceptions. The high valuation of the usefulness of the learning activities (98%) and the unanimous preference for practical methodologies reflect a significant shift away from the traditional approach centered on theoretical lectures.

These findings are consistent with those reported by Prince (2004) and Felder & Brent (2005), who highlight that PBL enhances student motivation, knowledge retention, and the contextual application of content. Likewise, the evidence gathered in this study supports the arguments presented by Smith (2019), demonstrating that students not only understood technical concepts but also developed essential soft skills such as teamwork, effective communication, and self-management.

In particular, the application of the Scrum methodology as a structural framework for group work was highly valued by students. This result aligns with the contributions of Kuz (2021), who emphasizes the relevance of Scrum in educational settings as a means of structuring real-world projects and fostering collaborative learning.

Nevertheless, several challenges were also identified. Qualitative feedback revealed the need for clearer role definitions within teams, as well as more differentiated assessment of individual contributions. This issue is critical for avoiding imbalances in workload distribution and for enhancing the perceived fairness of the evaluation process, as noted by Salmon (2000) and Dabbagh (2005).

Another relevant challenge concerned the degree of realism of the academic context. Although the course sought to simulate real software development scenarios, some students perceived the learning environment as still insufficiently representative of professional practice. This observation points to the need to strengthen collaboration with industry partners or real clients, as suggested by service-learning experiences and community-based project initiatives.

Finally, the experience confirms that the integration of authentic tools such as GitHub, MVC frameworks, and deployment platforms provides substantial pedagogical value by exposing students to current professional practices in the software industry. Their use in the classroom represents a significant opportunity to reduce the gap between academic training and labor market demands.

5. Conclusions

5.1. Conclusions

The implementation of Project-Based Learning (PBL) in the Software Engineering I course significantly improved students' perceptions of the usefulness, applicability, and dynamism of the teaching-learning process. The experience contributed to the development of both technical competencies and attitudinal skills, supporting a more comprehensive learning approach.

The integration of agile methodologies such as Scrum, together with the use of authentic development tools (e.g., GitHub, MVC frameworks, and web deployment platforms), added realism to the training process and strengthened student motivation. This was reflected in a high overall level of satisfaction (96%) and a unanimous preference for this approach over traditional teaching methods.

Despite these positive outcomes, the study also identified areas for improvement, including the need for clearer role definitions within teams, more frequent formative

feedback, and fairer assessment mechanisms that better recognize individual student contributions. 477
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5.2. Recommendations 479

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed: 480

First, the implementation of PBL should be extended to other technical courses within the Information Technology program, adapting its instructional design to the specific objectives and characteristics of each subject. 481
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Second, it is recommended to strengthen students' initial training in basic technical and soft skills, enabling them to successfully engage in collaborative work and agile methodologies from the early stages of their academic formation. 484
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Third, assessment mechanisms should be enhanced through the incorporation of specific rubrics that evaluate individual performance within group work, as well as the inclusion of peer-assessment and self-assessment strategies. 487
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Fourth, stronger links with the productive or institutional environment should be established, allowing student projects to address real needs of companies, organizations, or communities. This would further reinforce the practical and contextual components of learning. 490
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Finally, continuous professional development for instructors should be promoted, focusing on active learning methodologies, competency-based instructional design, and the use of project management technologies, in order to ensure a more effective curricular implementation of PBL. 494
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Appendix A. Semester Plan for the Software Engineering I Course 498

Table A1. Semester plan of the Software Engineering I course.

Session	Week, Duration, and Location	Topic	Learning Activities and Methodologies
1	Week 1, Day 1; 3 h; Classroom	Course introduction and diagnostic assessment	Instructor and student introductions; diagnostic test; syllabus and semester plan presentation (Inductive learning).
2	Week 1, Day 2; 2 h; Classroom	Syllabus and course project analysis	Collaborative discussion of syllabus, semester plan, and diagnostic results (Collaborative learning).
3	Week 2, Day 1; 3 h; Classroom	Introduction to Software Engineering and Agile Scrum	Lecture on software life cycle and Scrum; formation of Scrum teams (Lecture and guided discussion).
4	Week 2, Day 2; 3 h; Classroom/Virtual	Discussion of educational software crisis	Forum discussion based on a scientific article and introduction to the academic platform (Project-based learning).

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Session	Week, and Location	Duration,	Topic	Learning Activities and Methodologies
5	Week 3, Day 1; Classroom	2 h;	Forum execution (C1-1)	Recorded group discussion analyzing the assigned scientific article (Case-based learning).
6	Week 3, Day 2; Classroom/Virtual	2 h;	User stories and project exploration	System analysis and introduction to user stories (Experiential learning).
7	Week 4, Day 1; Classroom	2 h;	User story and prototype workshop	Workshop on user story creation and interface prototyping (Practical workshop).
8	Week 4, Day 2; Classroom	2 h;	Requirements presentation (A1-1)	Presentation of functional and non-functional requirements linked to user stories (Problem-based learning).
9	Week 5; Classroom		Software project management	Video-based analysis and guided discussion on software project management concepts (Active learning).
10	Week 5; Classroom		Scrum framework fundamentals	Critical reading and discussion of Scrum-related literature; assignment of autonomous activity C1-2 (Role-play and simulation).
11	Week 6; Classroom		Agile methodologies	Guided discussion and clarification of key concepts from the assigned scientific article (Guided practice).
12	Week 6; Classroom/Virtual		Forum on agile methodologies (C1-2)	Recorded group discussion analyzing agile practices and Scrum roles (Project-based learning).
13	Week 7; Classroom		Scrum dramatization planning	Analysis of previous dramatizations and planning of role-based Scrum enactments (Dramatization).
14	Week 7; Classroom		Scrum dramatization execution (B1-2)	Student-led enactment of Scrum processes following a predefined script (Dramatization).
15	Week 8; External environment		Behind-the-scenes interview (A1-2)	Reflective interviews on Scrum roles and responsibilities, recorded for assessment (Project-based learning).

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Session	Week, Duration, and Location	Topic	Learning Activities and Methodologies
16	Week 8; Classroom	First partial summative assessment	Written evaluation of theoretical and practical knowledge acquired during Units I and II (Summative assessment).
17	Week 9; Classroom	Software requirements and MVC architecture	Introduction to requirements documentation and MVC software architecture concepts (Theoretical–practical class).
18	Week 9; Classroom	Use cases and basic UML diagrams	Workshop on use case and entity–relationship diagram modeling (Project-based learning).
19	Week 10; Classroom	Advanced UML diagrams	Hands-on workshop on class and interface diagram development (Critical reading and debate).
20	Week 10; Classroom	MVC frameworks and PHP	Discussion and analysis of a scientific article on MVC-based PHP frameworks (Theoretical–practical class).
21	Week 11; Classroom/Virtual	Forum on MVC frameworks (C2-1)	Recorded academic discussion assessing comprehension of MVC framework concepts (Guided practice).
22	Week 11; Classroom/Virtual	GitHub and MVC framework setup	Creation of GitHub repositories and initial MVC framework deployment with tutorial support (Project-based learning).
23	Week 12; Classroom/Virtual	MVC application development (B2-1)	Development and deployment of an MVC-based web application managed through GitHub (Guided practice).
24	Week 12; Classroom	Technical presentation of MVC application (A2-1)	Student presentations explaining system architecture and implementation decisions (Constructive feedback).
25	Week 13; Classroom	Software sizing and estimation	Introduction to agile estimation techniques using story points and Planning Poker (Practical class).

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Session	Week, Duration, and Location	Topic	Learning Activities and Methodologies
26	Week 13; Classroom/Virtual	Project planning tools	Introduction to ClickUp for task planning and tracking of learning activities (Directed instruction).
27	Week 14; Classroom	Agile documentation practices	Critical discussion of scientific literature on agile documentation optimization (Guided practice).
28	Week 14; Classroom/Virtual	Forum on agile documentation (C2-2)	Recorded forum discussion analyzing best practices in Scrum documentation (Critical reading and debate).
29	Week 15; Classroom/Virtual	Application maintenance and evolution (B2-2)	Analysis and implementation of functional improvements to the developed web application (Lecture-based instruction).
30	Week 15; Classroom/Virtual	Software maintenance activities	Execution of maintenance tasks aligned with previously defined user stories (Project-based learning).
31	Week 16; Classroom	Final technical presentation (A2-2)	Student presentations summarizing system evolution and development outcomes (Project-based learning).
32	Week 16, Day 2; 2 h; Classroom	Final summative assessment	Final evaluation and student satisfaction survey administered online (Summative assessment).

Appendix B.

Appendix B.1.

Table A2. Summary of responses to the open-ended question on the teaching–learning process in the Software Engineering I course.

Category	Strengths	Weaknesses
Theory–practice integration	Enabled the application of theoretical concepts to real-world problems and addressed all stages of the software life cycle.	Need for additional practical activities that more closely reflect real professional challenges.

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Category	Strengths	Weaknesses
Teamwork	Promoted collaboration and collective problem-solving in authentic project contexts.	Limited clarity in role assignment, uneven assessment of individual contributions, and communication issues within teams.
Feedback	Existing feedback was perceived as valuable for learning.	Need for more frequent feedback during project development and greater emphasis on process evaluation rather than final outcomes only.
Tools and resources	Effective use of agile methodologies such as Scrum and collaborative tools such as GitHub; positive impact of frameworks explained in class.	Insufficient integration of more up-to-date software development tools.
Organization	Overall course methodology was perceived as well structured.	Need for improved project organization, task prioritization, clearer objectives, and more detailed guidelines.
Engagement and motivation	Motivating activities such as dramatizations and participation in academic fairs were highly valued.	Activities could be more dynamic to sustain engagement, and some students required greater commitment.
Real-world application	Project-Based Learning enabled students to experience realistic challenges, such as changing requirements and interaction with simulated clients.	Limited customization of methodologies to accommodate team-specific needs.
Assessment	Projects facilitated meaningful practical learning experiences.	Insufficient assessment of learning processes and soft skills, such as leadership and teamwork.
Infrastructure	Use of the computer laboratory supported step-by-step learning.	Laboratory resources could have been used more efficiently.
Initial training	Early introduction of the methodology helped build a solid foundation for learning.	Some students lacked sufficient initial preparation in theoretical concepts and basic skills.
Complexity and challenge	Challenging activities were positively valued by students.	Some learning activities could have been more complex to further enhance learning outcomes.

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